

**A STUDY OF THE PRAGMATIC DISCURSIVE ASPECTS OF
EUPHEMISMS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF
THE LEXICON OF BUSINESS ACTIVITIES)**

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Annotation

In this article, the author conducts a study of the pragmatic discursive aspects of euphemisms in the English language based on the lexicon of business activities. It identifies possible problems and provides solutions using specific examples.

Key words: Euphemism, discourse, thematic block, business idea, theoretical conclusion

Аннотация

В данной статье автор проводит исследование прагматических дискурсивных аспектов эвфемизмов в английском языке на основе лексики деловой активности. Он определяет возможные проблемы и предлагает решения с использованием конкретных примеров.

Ключевые слова: эвфемизм, дискурс, тематический блок, бизнес-идея, теоретический вывод.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada muallif ingliz tilidagi evfemizmlarning pragmatik diskursiv aspektlari tadqiqini tadbirkorlik faoliyati leksikasi asosida olib boradi. Unda uchrashiumkin bo'lgan muammolarni aniqlab, aniq misollar yordamida yechim beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Efimizm, diskurs, tematik blok, biznes g'oya, nazariy xulosa

Introduction: Problem statement. Euphemisms as a traditional form of renaming for the purpose of "blasphemy" are gaining extraordinary popularity in various spheres of modern communication, expanding their functional range. Since the object of the proposed research is euphemisms in business communication, we consider it necessary to precede the discussion of the material with some theoretical and methodological prerequisites that form the basis of our approach. Problems have been brought into the spotlight the status of business discourse in modern science, its species differentiation and the specifics of its function- in mass media communication, which is connected with the refinement of the metalanguage used. Studies of the last decade in the field of discursology are often conducted in the context of media linguistics and media criticism (L. I.Grishaeva, E. A. Kozhemyakin, T. G. Dobrosklonskaya, T. V. Chernyshova, A. G.

Pastukhov), revealing the interaction of discursive and medial traits. At the beginning of the XXI century there were radical changes in the understanding of the essential nature of the mass media, which led to the recognition, among other things, of the fact of the technological convergence of technical means of mass communication, acquiring a new typological property of mediality. Since the media environment is a natural sphere of functioning of many types of discourse, researchers rightly put on the agenda the problems of interaction of discourse, discursive practices, on the one hand, and medial means, on the other, correlating the medial order with the discursive order, social groups, speech behavior [1].

Methods In this kind of research, it is important to take into account that the medial media are extremely diverse, nationally. they are specific, culturally prioritized and creatively innovative, which affects the cultural and linguistic appearance of discourse in media communication. This assertion can be fully attributed to the business discourse, which allows us to approach its analysis in a differentiated manner, taking into account the format of implementation. It is this approach that we consider to be in demand today in the study of different types of business discourse in the media space, given the complex nature of modern mass communication and the social resonance of media texts. At the beginning of the third millennium , foreign sociology received a new impetus for development the theory of the so-called organizational communication, which represents a broad direction of research in the field of communication, ideology, public relations, leadership, culture and other aspects of companies' activities [2]. One of the most important theoretical results of the study of this type of communication was the conclusion about the heterogeneity, diversity and specificity of the functional purpose of the business discourse formed within corporate structures, which necessitated the development of its typology. Of the existing approaches to the classification of the concept attracts the attention of the left discourse the business discourse of Yu. V. Danyushina, developing the ideas of the American researcher W. C. Redding [3], the founder of organizational communication, about its basic postulates, which include business communication as a kind [4]. The author develops a functional typology, identifying the following subspecies of business discourse: educational and academic, business media discourse (or network business discourse), ritual and public, documentary and professional business discourse [5]. Describing the features of the established differences, the scientist, however, emphasizes the signs uniting them, ensuring the institutional nature of the business discourse.

Our study of euphemisms is limited to the discourse of business media, in which a personal factor is largely revealed, which is to increase the role of the mass addressee, increase the ideological load of business texts, create a multifunctional selection and evaluation of the realities of the business picture of the world, since modern mass media construct a social reality that suits the mass addressee the number of people living in a society torn apart by various kinds of contradictions increases many times the specific weight of linguistic resources that draw a favorable axiological picture of the simulated life. A special burden when performing this task falls on euphemisms as methods of forming a society free from social ills and evils in the mass consciousness. A significant proportion of social disasters have the causes of their occurrence in the vices of the organization of business activity, especially in the conditions of crisis conditions of the economy, an unfair system of distribution of national wealth and income received and other flaws of society. The modern world is impossible to imagine outside the framework of business relations, therefore, in the process of linguistic modeling, the role of linguistic means of shaping the discourse of business media is really extremely high, allowing to diagnose existing problems and predict the appearance of certain negative phenomena in this area in order to prevent their dangerous social consequences for society as a whole. In this study, the aim is to establish the specifics of the functioning of euphemisms in texts implementing the discourse of business media, which implies a structural and semantic analysis of euphemisms within the framework of the proposed thematic blocks, their semantic interpretation and identification of the frequency of appeal to them as indicators of the relevance of the concepts they replace. In the process of studying euphemisms in business media, in addition to the properties of institutional discourse [6], personal factors that ensure the effectiveness of communication and related to the emotional and evaluative component, traditions of national corporate culture, the social status of the target audience, situational circumstances are also taken into account. The evfemization of business discourse is actually it indicates the presence of one or another failure in the system organization and management of the company, in the imperfection of activities and the shadow sides of functioning. In the process of analyzing euphemisms, it is necessary to find out the factors of business situations that at certain stages experience crisis states that can generate negative reactions in society. Research materials and their analysis. To consider euphemisms in the discourse of business media, three thematic blocks are

identified. For analysis about 80 examples were selected from electronic English-language business media sources.

Thematic block "Unemployment and Dismissals" is represented by numerous euphemistic substitutions for the nomination of this problem. As follows from the name of the block covering situations related to job loss and the problem of unemployment in general, which is associated with stress and people's experiences in unstable times, the discourse of business media is implemented in hybrid texts [7], in which there is a convergence of features of social and business discourses.

Results Funemployment is a euphemism that replaces the designation of social disasters as a result of job loss (temporary or permanent). Analiz dictionary definition funemployment (a period of joblessness that a person uses for leisure and other fun activities) [8] shows that the euphemization mechanism in this case is triggered by the addition of semantic components of the corresponding, positive in their connotation: "fun" (amusement, enjoyment or pleasure) "employment" (the state of being employed) [9]. In the process of creating a euphemism that has the slang tag in the dictionary, a linguistic technique of occasional word formation using elements of a language game was used. EXAMPLE 1. For the record, Dustin approaches his sundry temporary jobs, which range from children's party clown to ice sculpture apprentice, with energy and enthusiasm...He's also quite content to take "employment" to heart, He enjoys having the leisure time to wage water balloon wars with the neighborhood kids and bask in the glow of the family's big-screen TV.

Contextual analysis of the example reveals the spread and strengthening of positive connotations of euphemism due to the connection of emotional intensities and connotatives, as well as the concretization of possible types of pleasant time-forwarding. The features of a text with a focus on topical social issues, allegedly legalized, are interwoven into the analyzed discourse to be solved by connecting various leisure options with the family, organizing fun games with neighborhood children and other amusements. The pragmatic context created by euphemism not only fills the picture with cultural meanings, but also implies an act of invitation to an open social discussion, which can take the form of a socially oriented dialogue. However, due to the recurring situations of recession in the economy, this image of a cheerful unemployed person begins to acquire ironic features of an "antihero from a comic book" [11], which causes associations with humorous discourse.

RIF (Reduction in Force) is a euphemism that is a literary form of nomination, meaning specific forms of dismissal and used in official corporate documents (layoffs, as used in official corporate documents and press releases; fire from a job) [12]. In this case, the euphemism is an abbreviation formed according to a fairly active model of word production in the English language based on the word combination "reduction in force" as a result of the action of two derivational processes: truncation and addition of truncated bases.

EXAMPLE 2. 'I've seen a lot of friends here today. People that I didn't know got RIFed. For most people, it was a shock," said Stark, who works on personal computers at the lab. The given example of a euphemism, borrowed from a blog, demonstrates the contextual transformation of the substantive basis, which is typical for the English language, converted into a glassy form, which, in the opinion of the creator of the text, is capable of veiling the negative connotation created by the general meaning of the components of the reduction (the dismissal of some of the employees caused by a lack of orders, lack of funds, reorganization of the enterprise, etc.; may occur in the form of dismissal, transfer to another position, demotion, dismissal for a certain period, going on vacation at your own expense, etc.) [7]. The context of using euphemism, unlike the previous example, does not sound so optimistic, because it shows that there are quite a lot of such people. Despite their employment in the field of computer technology, people are not immune from massive cuts. Topic it is socially relevant in society, since having a job is the key to success, a normal and stable life and respect for others. Therefore, people who are faced with this trouble do not like to talk about it openly, preferring different forms of masking an unpleasant fact. The thematic block "Financial problems of a company" includes euphemistic designations of the company's financial difficulties, which are different in nature, especially in connection with the financial and economic crisis experienced by Western economies in 2007-2008.

Discussion. kitchen-sink is a euphemism of metaphorical nature, used in direct meaning in discourse dramas (adjective (chiefly of drama) realistic in the department of drab or sordid subjects), and as a result functioning in a produced hybrid text representing the convergence of features of two types of discourse, which is clearly found in the example below at the lexical level.

EXAMPLE 3. Job cuts and a dividend reduction are thought to have already been factored into the share price. Equity salesmen believe that there is also little that could be said to push the shares higher on the day as the management has already kitchen-sunk the business and parted with Mariah Carey, one of its

most expensive stars [13]. Any question concerning the financial affairs of the company requires special attention. The slightest inaccuracies, and especially frauds with money, can affect the reputation of the organization. This example presents a fairly popular mechanism of euphemization based on the metaphorization of "drama in the kitchen", a household play about the unsightly sides of life. The metaphorical image distracts attention from the unpleasant news associated with the notification of a one time dismissal of all employees: to kitchen-sink to announce all of a company's bad financial news at one time. The use of euphemism in this context shifts the emphasis to a household item (kitchen sink), which evokes associations with a naturalistic household play about everyday problems. As is known, in the cultural tradition of the British, this image is preserved, left by the drama of J. Osborne's "Look Back in Anger", where almost all the action takes place in the kitchen. The technique of metaforization, by creating a parallel, is designed to soften the social resonance in society and preserve the prestige of the organization. Produced by the metaphor of the effect is based on the precedent use of this popular image in other spheres, which appeared for the first time in army jargon during the Second World War when describing intense bombing, when enemy artillery was shooting at anything, using kitchen sinks for shells.

2. Open-the-kimono is a euphemism of metaphorical origin. According to the dictionary definition (to open a company's accounting books for inspection; to expose something previously hidden). This phrase has received the status of a corporate term reveal details of one's business operations, declaring the company's obligation to disclose detailed information about its business transactions, carrying out business communication with partners without withholding information.

EXAMPLE 4, Most of the alliances, says Paolini, are legally formalized because of the need for both parties to "open the kimono" and discuss sales figures. proprietary research and financial figures [14].

In this case, the effect of euphemization is also based on the mechanism of metaphorization, fixing the created image in the cultural memory of the people, which is confirmed by the etymology of this expression. The expression originated in American business communication in the 1970s and became fixed in the language. There are several versions of its origin: (1) an open kimono means no any other clothing under it, which is further transferred to the close relationship between the spouses, having no secrets from each other; (2) an open kimono implies the absence of weapons hidden under clothing; (3) this is

one of the interpretations of the popular Japanese expression *yap. kamishimo wo nugu*, "without kamishimo", the official clothing of samurai. Samurai took off their top clothes in an informal setting, so the expression in Japanese means "relax, 1to speak sincerely". understand issues (e.g., should we use galvanized tin for the employees bicycle shed?). In the context of the euphemism used, the role of units emphasizing the meaning of, for given by a euphemism. The direct meaning of the concept of bike ("bicycle"), abstracted from this topic, makes it possible to soften the sharpness of the perception of the message and muffle the negative connotations of the text. "Shedding", as an integral part of euphemism, undergoes a generalization process, acquiring broad semantics: shedding, dumping, spreading. The combination of these bases in the composition of a complex word makes it possible to carry out a successful communication of veiling the unsightly sides, since the transfer of semantic emphasis thanks to the metaphorical image , it would be purely the above-mentioned problems, which cause rather an ironic smile (arguing about the color for painting the suspension under the bike before the completion of the house construction), avoids an acute critical assessment of the real shortcomings in the company's activities. The linguistic analysis of the above expression shows that the element *orep* in this combination, in addition to the main semantic components of the meaning "open" and "open", contains the most important components for the content of the terminological meaning: exposed to general view or knowledge: free from concealment. This qthe metaphorical meaning provides an indispensable manipulative effect on the mass consciousness, since it is assumed that we are talking about openness in receiving and transmitting business information, which implies the absence of hidden unsightly facts about the company and its activities.

Conclusion. Thus, as a result of the study, the specifics of the functioning of euphemisms in the discourse of business media were determined, and the nature of the formation of business euphemisms within the thematic blocks in the financial and economic sphere, most susceptible to the processes of euphemization, was revealed. The relative activity of using techniques for creating euphemistic nominations in contexts requiring strict control in the media industry has been established traveling and dictating an acceptable format for a pub-personal discussion of pain points in the economy. Judging by the results of quantitative calculations, the most active substitution of euphemisms for negative phenomena occurs in the sphere of nomination of financial problems, which is confirmed by dictionary data and neoplasms. The

mechanism of metaphorization, which is a popular way of producing euphemisms in the English language discourse of business media, has the result of providing a cognitive and ethno cultural basis for creating hybrid business media texts in which convergence is observed- a combination of features of different types of discourse. The conducted analysis confirms this pattern on the basis of the convergence of the properties of business discourse and social, theatrical, ironic discourse.

The study of business euphemisms in the media space shows their role in the process of linguistic construction of reality. In this capacity, the participation of euphemisms in the creation of a favorable axiological picture is most clearly manifested, obscuring the social evils of modern society and imposing the myth of a society of social equality and universal welfare on the mass consciousness.

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